

THE EFFECT OF SEAWEED ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF JUTE FIBER/VINYL ESTER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Recently, as environmental problems have arisen due to plastic pollution and waste problem, eventually interest in environmentally friendly materials is increasing. However, research on the strength of environmentally friendly and the interfacial adhesion of composites is lacking. Therefore, in this study, we tried to improve mechanical properties by extracting nano fibres from seaweed, an eco-friendly material, and using it as an additive in the process of manufacturing eco-friendly composites. Nano fibres extracted from seaweeds are expected to be widely used when they are effective in improving mechanical properties because they are easy to manufacture and inexpensive. As a result, in this study natural fiber composite materials were prepared by using nano-fibers extracted from seaweeds as additives and the effects of additives on mechanical properties were evaluated. The mechanical properties i.e., tensile, bending and impact properties were improved. This means that the seaweed fiber was successfully extracted and is expected to be effective in improving the interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the resin. Therefore, it was confirmed that the seaweed fibers developed through this study are effective for improving the physical properties of natural fiber composite materials and can be manufactured at a low cost, thus being environmentally friendly and economical, and can be applied to various fields through subsequent studies can be expected.

1 INTRODUCTION

The incredible amount of plastic garbage that is generated every year has been a problem for many years because it takes a long time to decompose, and the damage to the ingested creatures is becoming serious. In recent years, the disposal of waste plastics has become a major problem due to the degradation due to sunlight and environment [1-3]. It is expected that microplastics will accumulate in the human body and threaten their health because they are ingested by plankton and eventually consumed by humans along the food chain [4]. In order to overcome these disadvantages of plastics and to minimize the environmental impact, eco-friendly resins and composites with biodegradability have been developed. However, due to the hydrophilicity of the natural fibers, there is a disadvantage in that the interfacial adhesion strength with the resin having the hydrophobic property is lowered, which limits the application of the environmentally friendly composite material. In order to overcome this, various studies have been made to improve the interfacial adhesion between the resin and the matrix by improving the hydrophobicity through the surface treatment of natural fibers. The use of nanoparticles such as MWCNT was effective in improving the properties of natural fiber composites [5], but it was inefficient in terms of cost. The purpose of this study is to improve the mechanical properties of nano - fibers after extracting them from environmentally friendly seaweeds. Nanofibers extracted from seaweeds are expected to be widely used when they are effective in improving mechanical properties because they are easy to manufacture and inexpensive.

2 RESEARCH METHOD

2.1 Extraction of nanofibers

Impurities were removed from natural seaweed, which is a raw material, and nanofibers were extracted and used as an additive in the production of composite materials. First, seaweed is added to distilled water, boiled sufficiently, and then washed in clear water to remove impurities and freeze-dried to remove moisture. After that, bleaching was performed using an oxygen bleaching agent, and the cellulose was boiled in an aqueous solution of 5 wt.% Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) for 4 hours to separate the cellulose from the other components. Next, the cellulose was extracted using a vacuum filter, washed repeatedly until the pH became neutral, and finally, the ethanol extraction was completed by removing moisture using an ethanol replacement method. This process is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Fiber Extraction Process.

2.2 Dispersion of nanofibers

In order to disperse the nanofiber additive into the matrix, a 3 roll mill was used, which is a device for crushing and dispersing nanomaterials effectively using shear forces of rotating rolls in different directions and speeds. The rotation speed of the machine was 200 RPM and 5 or 6 repetitions were performed so that the additive was dispersed sufficiently in the resin. Fig. 2 is a schematic view of a three roll-mill. Additives were mixed in the proportions of 0.1wt%, 0.3wt% and 0.5wt%, respectively, and the mixed resin was used for the preparation of the composite material

Figure 2: Schematic view of Three-Roll-Mill.

Figure 3: Process Diagram of hand-layup

2.3 Hand-Layup Process

Various processes are available for the production of composite materials. However, when a resin mixed with an additive is used, the molding process in which the resin is injected can't be used because the additive is filtered by the fibers. In this study, composite materials were fabricated using the hand-layup method, which is a classical composite material manufacturing process. This process has a disadvantage in that the volume fraction of the fibers is lower than that of the VARTM (Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding) process, but the additives can be uniformly dispersed in the matrix. The specific hand layup procedure is as follows. First, the surface of the mold to be laminated with natural fibers was thoroughly polished / washed and subjected to mold release treatment. Thereafter, four pieces of jute fibers were laminated on the mold surface. In the process of laminating the fibers, Fig. 3, a roller and a brush were used to spread the resin mixed with the accelerator to the reinforcement.

2.4 Mechanical Properties Evaluation

Mechanical properties of the natural fiber composites were investigated in order to investigate the effect of addition of seaweed nanofibers on the mechanical properties of natural fiber composites. Tensile test, 3 point bending test and drop-weight impact test were conducted according to ASTM D3039, ASTM D790, and ASTN D7136 standards, respectively. For the tensile test, the test speed of 1 mm / min was used and the change of the gauge distance of the parallel part of the tensile test specimen was precisely measured using an extensometer. For the bend test, the support distance was set to 16 times the specimen thickness and the test speed was 1.36 mm / min. For the drop impact test, the drop energy of the impactor according to the thickness of the specimen was calculated and the impact height was calculated in conjunction with the position energy formula. The impact energy used in the test was 21J.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Shape of the Extracted Additive

The SEM image of the fiber additive extracted from seaweeds confirmed the fiber shape with a diameter of 2 ~ 3 μm . The diameter of the fiber was relatively constant.

(a) Seaweed Cellulose

(b) X 100 Magnification

(c) X 1000 Magnification

Figure 4: SEM Image of Extracted Seaweed Fiber.

3.2 Tensile Behavior

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 shows the tensile behavior of nanocomposites prepared by adding nanofibers. The tensile strength was highest when 0.1% of nanofibers were added, and gradually decreased when added more. Composite materials prepared using only jute fibers without added nanofibers had an average tensile strength of 34 MPa, but with nanofibers, the tensile strength increased up to 45 MPa, which is an improvement of about 24%. The modulus of elasticity increased slightly with the addition of nanofibers.

Figure 5: Tensile Behavior of Nanocomposites.

Figure 6: Tensile Properties of nanocomposites.

3.3 Bending Behavior

Fig. 7 shows the result of the three-point bending test of the nanocomposite material. The flexural strength increased with increasing the content of nanofibers unlike the tensile test results. In the case of no addition of nanofibers, the addition of about 87 MPa, 0.5% % Increase in flexural strength. The fracture toughness tended to be proportional to the bending strength and increased up to 12% compared to the case without nanofibers. This means that the nanofibers extracted from seaweed are effective in improving the flexibility of natural fiber composite materials..

(a) Flexural Strength

(b) Fracture Displacement

Figure 7: The Results of Three-Point Bending Test

3.4 Low-Speed Impact Behavior

Fig. 8 shows the comparison of collapse impact behavior when no nanofibers are added and when 0.5% is added. The maximum impact loads were 1281 and 1543 N, respectively, and the difference was about 17%. First, the impact behavior of JFRP shows that after the impact, the load gradually increases and then falls sharply from the maximum value. This indicates that the resistance to impact is relatively low. On the other hand, when 0.5% of nanofibers were added, the maximum value of the load appeared in a shorter time, and the load gradually decreased gradually after the maximum value, indicating that the impact strength was greatly improved.

Next, the shock absorption behavior of JFRP showed a tendency to decrease rapidly after absorbing about 3.3 J of energy. This means that after the JFRP was impacted, the specimen suddenly ruptured without great resistance and penetrated. On the other hand, when 0.5% nanofibers were added, energy was absorbed up to about 3 J, then absorbed energy up to about 3.7 J while repeating falling and rising. These behaviors appear to occur when the impacted composite material is not broken at one time and

gradually broken down. The larger the crack length, the more consistent the explanation is obtained through the study [6] which absorbed much impact.

Through the impact load and the energy absorption behavior of the composite material, it was confirmed that the impact properties of the nanofiber-added composite material were greatly improved.

(a) Load-Time Curve (b) Absorbed Energy-Time Curve

Figure 8: The Results of Drop Weight Impact Test

3.5 Fracture Surface Analysis

Fig. 9 and 10 are photographs taken by scanning electron microscope of fracture sections of JFRP and 0.5% added nanofibers. In the case of no addition of nanofibers (Fig. 9 (a)), many traces of jute fibers were observed, but when nanofibers were added, jute fibers were often broken together with the polymer. This is expected to be due to the improved interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the matrix, and the strength of the fiber is higher than that of the matrix, leading to improved properties.

The mechanism of property improvement is shown in Fig. 11, it was confirmed by observing the surface of the natural fiber in the fractured specimen. The surface of jute fibers of JFRP without addition of nanofibers is very smooth, and the resistance against the generation of fibers due to the load is very small. However, Fig. As shown in Fig. 10 (b), when the nanofibers were added to the surface of the jute fibers, the surface roughness of the nanofibers increased, which may have affected the interfacial adhesion strength or interfacial shear strength.

Since the natural fiber is a hydrophilic material, the bond strength with the matrix is generally lowered. However, since the nanofibers extracted from the seaweed are also hydrophilic, they are considered to be well bonded with the jute fibers, and as a result, they have improved the overall mechanical properties.

(a) JFRP (b) 0.5% Seaweed

Figure 8: SEM Image of Fracture Surface

(a) JFRP

(b) 0.5% Seaweed

Figure 9: Observation of the Surface of Jute Fiber

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, a natural fiber composite material using nanofibers extracted from seaweeds as additives was prepared and the effects of additives on the mechanical properties were evaluated. The conclusion is as follows.

The addition of seaweed nanofibers to natural fiber composites has helped to improve tensile, bending and impact properties, which means that nanofibers have been successfully extracted. However, the mechanical behavior of nanofibers was different. Tensile strength was the highest when nanofibers were added within 0.1%, and bending and impact strength were highest when 0.5% of nanofibers were added. These results indicate that nanofibers should be used in conjunction with natural fibers, with appropriate ratios taking into account the type of application and load.

The seaweed nanofiber developed through this study is expected to be applicable to various fields through subsequent studies since it is not only effective in improving the physical properties of natural fiber composite materials, but also has environmental friendliness and economy.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kara Lavender Law, Richard C. Thompson, Microplastics in the seas, *Science*, 345, 2014, pp. 144-145
- [2] Julia Fahrenkamp-Uppenbrink, Seas are awash with microplastics, *Science*, 345, 2014, pp. 175-177
- [3] Sacha Vignieri, Microplastic's triple threat, *Science*, 352, 2016, pp. 1185
- [4] R.H. Waring, R.M. Harris, S.C. Mitchell, Plastic contamination of the food chain: A threat to human health?, *Maturitas*, 115, 2018, pp. 64-68
- [5] K.Mohan, T Rajmohan, Effects of MWCNT on Mechanical Properties of Glass-Flax Fiber Reinforced Nano Composites, *ScienceDirect*, 5, 2018, pp. 11628-11635
- [6] D.W.Lee, B.J. Park, J.I. Song, Fabrication of High-Stiffness Fiber Metal Laminates and Study of Their Behavior Under Low-Velocity Impact Loadings, *Composite Structures*, 189, 2018, pp. 61-69